

Stability Constants of the Ternary Complexes System : M(II)—Amino Acids—Quinolines

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Manuscript received 17 November 1992, accepted 12 January 1993

Solution equilibria of the biologically important system Co^{II} -, Ni^{II} - and Cu^{II} - mono- and dicarboxylic amino acids and/or some quinoline derivatives are investigated by the pH-titration technique. Formation of the 1 : 1 : 1 mixed-ligand complexes is inferred and stability of these complexes are determined at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and $\mu=0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaClO_4). Generally, it is deduced that the ternary complex is more stable than the corresponding binary metal-quinoline complex. Further, the stability of the binary and ternary complexes are examined and discussed.

Quinolines are considered as an important class of compounds in many fields of applications, mainly chelatometry, separation methods and biological applications¹. Moreover, it was recognised that the biological activities of substituted quinolines relate to their abilities to form metal chelates². On the other hand, formation of ternary complexes plays an important role in analytical chemistry and in biological processes³. Accordingly, study of mixed-ligand metal complexes containing quinoline derivatives is considered as an important effort to understand their metal ion complexation in the biological systems. Therefore, study of the metal complexes of quinoline compounds in binary as well as in ternary systems received much attention⁴. However, little attention has been paid to mixed-ligand complexes of the two biologically important ligands, quinolines and amino acids^{5,6}. Accordingly, the present work is devoted to a systematic study on the ternary system of divalent transition metal ions (Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II}): mono- and dicarboxylic amino acids, HL or H_2L (glycine, alanine, valine, asparagine, glutamine, aspartic and glutamic acids): quinolines, L' (quinoline, 6-methoxyquinoline and 6-methylquinoline) by making use of the pH-metric technique.

Results and Discussion

Representative set of experimental titration curves obtained according to the sequence described in the experimental section for the different M(II): amino acids: quinolines systems studied are displayed in Figs. 1 and 2. Examination of these figures reveals the formation of the different M(II)-quinolines binary complexes in the pH range 3.7–5.0. This is attained from the appeared divergence of each of the 1 : 1 binary M(II)-quinolines titration curve from that of the corresponding free quinoline solution. Generally, such complexes are stable up to pH 8.5, 7.8 and 5.5 for Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} respectively. Beyond these pH values, hydrolysis of the complexes leads to the

formation of hydroxo complex species. Therefore, in such case, a further study above these pH values could not be possible.

For the titration curves of the other M(II)-amino acids binary complexes, it is evident that these complexes begin to form in the pH range 3.5–6.5 and 2.75–4.0 for mono- and dicarboxylic amino acids respectively. It is worth mentioning that for all the 1 : 1 Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} -amino acids binary complexes, precipitation occurred at high pH (9.0–10.5, 8.0–9.0 and 7.0–7.5 respectively).

Careful examination of the titration curves of the ternary complexes reveals that the 1 : 1 : 1 mixed-ligand complexes are formed at pH values lower than those corresponding to the formation of the binary complexes of the quinolines. This behaviour indicates that the binary complex ML is firstly formed and it coordinates with quinolines (L') as secondary ligand to yield the mixed-ligand complex (MLL') in a stepwise manner,

Thus, it can be considered that the secondary ligand (quinoline, 6-methoxyquinoline, 6-methylquinoline) combines with $[\text{ML}]^+$ or $[\text{ML}]$ binary complex species in ternary system just as it does with $[\text{M}(\text{H}_2\text{O}_6)]^{2+}$ binary system. As such, the horizontal distance between curves-c and -f (for curve-f an equivalent volume of NaOH to the amount of quinoline present in the medium is added to the consumed volumes of NaOH at all pHs) is measured and used for the calculation of the formation constants of different 1 : 1 : 1 ternary complexes. In this respect it is worthy to mention that the binary M(II)-amino acid complexes are stable up to the pH range where the attachment of the secondary ligand, quinoline derivatives, takes place forming the ternary complexes. For all the ternary metal complex solutions, precipitation occurred at pH

Fig. 1. Titration curves for the ternary system Cu^{II} : valine: 6-methylquinoline at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and $\mu = 0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaClO_4): (a) $0.17592 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ HClO}_4$, (b) solution (a) $+ 5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ of 6-methylquinoline, (c) solution (b) $+ 5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ of Cu^{II} , (d) solution (a) $+ 5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ of valine, (e) solution (d) $+ 5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ of Cu^{II} and (f) solution (e) $+ 5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ of 6-methylquinoline.

range 6.5–8.5 depending on the nature of both amino acid and quinoline as well as metal ion. Therefore, studies were performed only up to this pH range in order to avoid the interference of the most likely formed hydroxo complex species.

Stability constants: The stability constants of the 1:1 binary and 1:1:1 ternary complexes in the ternary system were calculated^{7,8} from the results of the pH-titrimetric method; only second and third acid dissociation constant values of the different mono- and dicarboxylic amino acids were used in the calculation. However, the first acid dissociation constant values of these amino acids are too low (~ 2)⁹ which exist only in strongly acidic solution, therefore it was not used in the

calculation. The mean $\log K_{\text{ML}}^{\text{M}}$, $\log K_{\text{ML}}^{\text{ML}}$ and $\log K_{\text{MLL}}^{\text{ML}}$ values obtained from the corresponding experimental titration curves are listed in Tables 1 and 2. The results reveal that the stability of the same metal ion binary and ternary complexes is little influenced by changing the nature of the quinoline derivatives. This is in accordance with the little variation in basicity of the quinolines ($\text{p}K_{\text{a}} = 5.17, 5.05$ and 4.94 for 6-methylquinoline, 6-methoxyquinoline and quinoline respectively). On the other hand, the stability of the binary and ternary complexes of monocarboxylic amino acids generally follows the order: glycine ($\text{p}K_{\text{a}} = 9.78$) > alanine ($\text{p}K_{\text{a}} = 9.87$) > valine ($\text{p}K_{\text{a}} = 9.74$) > asparagine ($\text{p}K_{\text{a}} = 8.80$) > glutamine ($\text{p}K_{\text{a}} = 9.28$). More-

Fig. 2. Titration curves for the ternary system CuII : aspartic acid : 6-methylquinoline at 25° and $\mu=0.2$ mol dm⁻³ (NaClO₄) : (a) 0.17592 mol dm⁻³ of HClO₄, (b) solution (a) + 5×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ of 6-methylquinoline, (c) solution (b) + 5×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ of CuII, (d) solution (a) + 5×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ of aspartic acid, (e) solution (d) + 5×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ of CuII and (f) solution (e) + 5×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ of 6-methylquinoline.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANT DATA FOR THE BINARY M(II)-COMPLEXES OF QUINOLINES AND AMINO ACIDS (log K_{ML}^M AND log K_{ML}^M)

Temp. = 25 ± 0.1°, $\mu=0.2$ mol dm⁻³ (NaClO₄)

Compd.	log K_{ML}^M			log K_{ML}^M		
	CoII	NiII	CuII	CoII	NiII	CuII
Quinoline	2.60	2.70	3.00	—	—	—
6-Methoxyquinoline	2.65	2.70	3.13	—	—	—
6-Methylquinoline	2.70	2.72	3.15	—	—	—
Glycine	—	—	—	5.20	6.12	8.40
Alanine	—	—	—	5.10	5.77	8.28
Valine	—	—	—	5.03	5.75	8.20
Asparagine	—	—	—	4.50	5.62	7.94
Glutamine	—	—	—	4.05	5.30	7.78
Glutamic acid	—	—	—	4.70	5.90	8.34
Aspartic acid	—	—	—	6.07	7.34	8.81

over, the stability of the binary and ternary complexes containing the dicarboxylic amino acids aspartic ($pK_{a2}=3.86$, $pK_{a3}=9.80$) is higher than that of the corresponding complexes containing the dicarboxylic acid ($pK_{a2}=4.31$, $pK_{a3}=9.67$). This behaviour, in general, can be interpreted in terms of the effective basicity of the conjugate base of these amino acids as well as the steric effects. Generally, increase in the amino acid chain-length would result in more strain on its bending, i.e. relatively low stability. It is worthy to note that some of the log K values of the binary M(II)-amino acid complexes under investigation are in good agreement with those found in the literature^{6,8,10}. In addition, the stability of the mixed-ligand complexes containing each of the primary ligand dicarboxylic amino acids (aspartic and glutamic)

TABLE 2—STABILITY CONSTANT DATA FOR THE TERNARY COMPLEXES

Temp. = 25 ± 0.1° and $\mu = 0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaClO₄)

Amino acid	$\log K_{MLL}^{ML}$								
	Quinoline			6-Methoxyquinoline			6-Methylquinoline		
	CoII	NiII	CuII	CoII	NiII	CuII	CoII	NiII	CuII
Glycine	5.13	5.97	8.10	5.54	6.20	8.20	5.73	6.20	8.47
Alanine	5.00	5.93	8.00	5.25	6.08	8.05	5.73	6.15	8.47
Valine	4.62	5.90	7.88	5.10	6.05	8.05	5.15	6.10	8.40
Asparagine	4.62	5.85	7.80	4.70	5.95	7.70	4.73	5.98	7.90
Glutamine	4.25	5.55	7.70	4.65	5.55	7.70	4.68	5.55	7.70
Glutamic acid	8.15	8.20	9.10	8.10	8.25	9.20	8.15	8.30	9.25
Aspartic acid	8.65	8.80	9.55	8.80	9.10	9.60	9.10	9.15	9.65

is higher than that of the corresponding one containing monocarboxylic amino acid. This can be mainly ascribed to the effective high basicity of the dicarboxylic amino acid, i.e. good σ -donor, as well as its expected high tendency to act as O, N, O tridentate ligands where two chelated rings are formed.

Furthermore, the ternary complexes are characterised by high stability compared to the corresponding M(II)-quinoline binary complexes. This can be explained on the principle of the expected lower electrostatic repulsion during the addition of the secondary ligand, quinoline derivatives, to the binary M(II)-amino acid complex (c.f. equation 2) relative to that of the aqua-metal ion ($M(H_2O)_6^{+2} + [HL]^{+1} \rightleftharpoons [ML]^{+2} + H^+$). In addition, the ternary complex contains one or two chelate rings as a result of the coordination of the primary ligand for mono- and dicarboxylic amino acid respectively. This in turn results in a high stability of the ternary complex compared to the corresponding binary M(II)-quinoline complexes.

In terms of the nature of the divalent transition metal ion, it is evident that the stability of different binary or ternary complexes in the systems under investigation increases in the direction: $Co^{II} \rightarrow Ni^{II} \rightarrow Cu^{II}$. This is in accordance with the expected order of the stability of the complexes of these metal ions¹¹.

Experimental

Metal salts ($CuCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$, $NiCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ and $CoCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$), and quinoline derivatives as well as amino acids were of A.R. grade (Aldrich and Janssen) with purity not less than 98% and were used as such. All other chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Stock solutions ($5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) of the divalent metal salts, amino acids and quinolines were prepared in CO₂-free double-distilled water. NaOH solution ($\sim 0.3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) was prepared in carbonate-free double-distilled water and standardised against a standard KH-phthalate solution. A stock solution (0.4 mol dm^{-3}) of NaClO₄ used as a supporting electrolyte, was prepared in double distilled water. Generally,

dilute solutions were prepared by appropriate dilution of the stock solutions.

pH-metric titration: Titrations with standardised carbonate-free NaOH solution of different M(II)-amino acids and/or quinolines mixtures in a 1:1:1 molar ratio ($5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ for each) were performed at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. A constant ionic strength was maintained at 0.2 mol dm^{-3} (NaClO₄) and total volume was kept at 50 ml. The change in the pH values of the titrated solutions was followed with an Orion 701A pH-meter with a combined glass-calomel electrode. The electrode system was calibrated before and after each series of pH-measurements under the same conditions by using standard buffers at 25° . The different solutions titrated can be represented according to the following scheme; (a) HClO₄ + NaClO₄; (b) solution (a) + quinolines; (c) solution (b) + M(II); (d) solution (a) + amino acids; (e) solution (d) + M(II); (f) solution (e) + quinolines.

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